

MICROSTRUCTURAL DEVELOPMENT OF LIME-METAKAOLIN PASTES WITH ACCELERATING AGENTS IN EARLY AGE

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ABSTRACT

Lime-pozzolan mortars are indicated for interventions in old buildings, but studies have pointed their slow hardening. This work aims to evaluate the microstructural development, in early age, of lime and metakaolin pastes, in the proportion by mass of 50%-50%, using the following accelerating agents: commercial set accelerating admixture (0,5% by mass), calcium chloride (5% and 10% by mass) and 1% of cement. The microstructures of 3 and 7 days were assessed using X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscopy. The accelerators agents did not result in formation of different products and monocarboaluminate was the main hydration product.

KEYWORDS

Lime; Metakaolin; Setting time; Microstructure; Accelerating admixture.

INTRODUCTION

Historical buildings in some time of its service life need conservation and restauration services due to ambient conditions and human use. Regarding the use of binders in the mortars of these buildings, Portland cement is not recommended to contribute with high mechanical strength, high modulus of elasticity, low permeability to water vapor and the presence of alkaline hydroxides in the mortars that can react forming soluble salts (Gameiro, Santos Silva, Veiga, & Velosa, 2012; Seabra, Paiva, Labrincha, & Ferreira, 2009).

In these cases, it is recommended to use durable conservation materials with behavior close to the original materials (M. R. Veiga, Velosa, & Magalhães, 2009). Lime-based mortars were extensively used in the past and their technology has been rescued for application (Gameiro et al., 2014, 2012). However, lime mortars have some drawbacks such as slow hardening, high shrinkage and low strength (Nežerka et al., 2014).

Studies on lime or lime and pozzolans mortars cover several aspects, such as the behavior of different types of lime (Zhang et al., 2018), curing conditions (Azeredo, Struble, & Carneiro, 2015; Grilo et al., 2014), types of pozzolanic additions (Walker & Pavía, 2011), proportion of materials (Gameiro et al., 2012), types of aggregates (Arizzi, Martínez-Huerta, Sebastián-Pardo, & Cultrone, 2015), use of admixtures (Seabra et al., 2009), rheology (Fourmentin et al., 2015; Sales et al., 2021), among others.

The inclusion of pozzolans in its composition improves performance in terms of water permeability, durability, mechanical strength and reduction in hardening time (Arizzi & Cultrone, 2018; Azeredo et al., 2015), with metakaolin being the pozzolanic material usually studied (Aggelakopoulou, Bakolas, & Moropoulou, 2011; Arizzi & Cultrone, 2012, 2018; Azeredo et al., 2015; Gameiro et al., 2014, 2012; Grilo et al., 2014; Nežerka et al., 2014; B. A. Silva, Ferreira Pinto, & Gomes, 2014).

However, the reduction is still very small in relation to Portland cement-based materials. The works cite demould dates of 5-7 days (Izaguirre, Lanas, & Álvarez, 2011; Pérez-Nicolás et al., 2016; B. Silva, Ferreira Pinto, Gomes, & Candeias, 2019). In addition, the time required for the application and drying of the multilayers is still pointed out as a limitation for the consolidation of the use of lime mortars (R. Veiga, 2017).

In pastes and mortars based on air lime and pozzolan, in addition to lime carbonation, the development of microstructure occurs associated with pozzolanic reaction. The main compounds formed in lime and metakaolin mortars and pastes resulting from the pozzolanic reaction with calcium hydroxide are hydrated calcium aluminates and silicoaluminates such as stratlingite (C_2ASH_8), hidrogarnet (C_3AH_6), monocarboaluminate (C_4ACH_{11}), as well as CSH and C_4AH_{13} (Arizzi & Cultrone, 2012; Azeredo et al., 2015; Gameiro et al., 2014, 2012; B. A. Silva et al., 2014).

Therefore, the objective of this work is to study the influence of different hardening accelerating agents on the formation of hydration compounds and, therefore, on the microstructural development of the pastes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used were type I Hydrated Lime – CHI (ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE NORMAS TÉCNICAS (ABNT), 2003)(NBR 7175, ABNT 2003), metakaolin produced from calcination in the laboratory of kaolin (below $45\mu m$ mesh sieve) at $700^\circ C$ for two hours (MK) and water supplied by the local distribution network. CP V-ARI cement (NBR 16697, ABNT 2011), Sika-3 Plus brand set accelerator admixture, yellowish color and calcium chloride ($CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$) in powder for analysis were used as hardening accelerators agents. The materials were obtained from market in the cities of Campina Grande and João Pessoa, Paraíba, Brazil.

From the physical properties, unit mass, specific mass (NBR 16605, ABNT 2019) and laser granulometry were performed. Table 1 shows the results of the physical analyses performed on the materials used. Regarding to the setting accelerator admixture, the pH of 6.0 ± 1.0 and the specific mass were obtained from the product's technical sheet (Sika, 2020).

Table 1: Specific Mass and Unit Mass

Material	Specific Mass (g/cm^3)	Unit Mass (g/cm^3)
Hydrated Lime (L)	2.22	0.37
Metakaolin (MK)	2.54	0.43
Calcium chloride (Cc)	-	-
Commercial setting accelerator admixture (A)	-	-
Portland Cement (Ce)	3.09	0.91

Laser granulometry was performed in CILAS model 1090 equipment. The granulometric curves and respective histograms of the materials are in Figure 1. The analysis of the chemical composition of the fine materials was determined in a semi-quantitative way using the fluorescence spectrometer of X-rays, in a SHIMADZU equipment, model 720 (Table 2).

Figure 1: Granulometric Distribution

Table 2: Chemical composition by x-ray fluorescence and pozzolanic activity of materials

Chemical composition (%)											
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	TiO ₂	Others	LOI**
Lime	0.97	0.82	0.16	83.66	5.10	-	-	0.48	-	0.01	8.80
MK	45.11	52.75	0.10	-	-	0.06	-	0.28	-	0.10	1.60
									CC	Ref.*	
Pozzolanic activity index with lime (MPa)									6.17	> 6.0	

*Normative value NBR 12653 (ABNT, 2012); **Loss of ignition.

In relation to lime, the sum of CaO and MgO on a non-volatile basis is equivalent to 97% and it can be classified as CH-I, based on NBR 7175 (ABNT, 2003). CK, according to NBR 12653 (ABNT, 2014), can be classified as Class N pozzolanic material, as it has a SO₃ content lower than 4%, and a sum of SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ greater than 70%. The pozzolanic activity of MK with lime at 7 days was also evaluated following NBR 5751 (ABNT, 2015). The average strength was 6.17 MPa, therefore above the parameter of 6 MPa established to be considered as pozzolanic material, according to NBR 12653 (ABNT, 2012).

Mineralogical characterization was performed by X-ray diffraction in a SHIMADZU equipment, Lab X/XRD-6000 model under the following test conditions: CuK α radiation of wavelength $\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$ with X-rays at 30kv and 30mA, power of 2kVA, reading speed of 1 $^\circ$ /min in a range of 5 $^\circ$ to 65 $^\circ$ 2 θ at an angular step of 0.02 $^\circ$ 2 θ . Figure 2 shows the diffractograms of hydrated lime and metakaolin.

Figure 2: X-ray diffraction of materials

In the hydrated lime diffractogram the main constituent phases are portlandite (CaOH_2) and calcite (CaCO_3). Metakaolin is composed of quartz and illite. The absence of kaolinite peaks shows that the temperature and duration of the calcination was adequate. A halo between 20 and 30° (2θ) can be seen on the MK XRD indicating the material's amorphity.

PASTES PREPARATION

The adopted lime: MK ratio was fixed at 1:1 (by mass) based on previous studies (Fortes-Revilla, Martínez-Ramírez, & Blanco-Varela, 2006; Gameiro et al., 2014; Papayianni & Stefanidou, 2006; Velosa, Veiga & Rocha, 2009). Table 3 shows the details of the mixtures for the tests and the water/binder contents were fixed at 1.0 (Bakolas, Aggelakopoulou, Moropoulou, & Anagnostopoulou, 2006). The percentage of additives was defined as 1% for Portland Cement, 5% and 10% for CaCl_2 and 0.5% for the commercial accelerator admixture, all them in relation to the sum mass of the lime and pozzolan. Ensaios de Mini-cone foram realizados para observar por meio da medição do espalhamento como os aditivos influenciaram na demanda de água das pastas.

Table 3: Pastes compositions

Paste	Mass Proportion (%)		Mass proportion in relation to binder (%)		
	Lime	Metakaolin	Portland cement	CaCl_2	Commercial admixture
LMK	50	50	-	-	-
LMKCe	50	50	1	-	-
LMKc5	50	50	-	5	-
LMKc10	50	50	-	10	-
LMKA	50	50	-	-	0,5

**Abbreviations: L = Lime; MK = Metakaolin; Ce = Portland cement; Cc = calcium chloride; A = Commercial setting accelerator admixture.*

The preparation of the mixtures for the Mini-slump, XRD and MEV tests followed the same procedure, which was based on the step-by-step presented in NBR 14399 (ABNT, 1999). Before starting, the dry powder was manually mixed for 2 minutes, as shown in the work by (Sérgio Filho, Sinhorelli, Medeiros, Azeredo, & Azeredo, 2020). Then, water was added to the empty container and then the dry materials were placed. After the introduction of all dry material, we waited 30 seconds and mechanical mixing was started for 90 seconds, with the aid of a Philco brand mixer and 600 W power at maximum speed. With the mixer off, the walls of the container and the rod were scraped and then mixing was restarted for another 90 seconds. In mixtures that contained the CaCl_2 or admixture, they were pre-mixed in water. In the case of cement, this was mixed together with the dry materials.

XRD tests at 3 and 7 days of curing and SEM at 7 days were performed to evaluate the products formed in the pastes. The samples were prepared as presented above and then placed in a plastic ice mold with a lid. To avoid water loss and to submit the samples to wet curing, the mold was covered and wrapped in 2 damp cloths and cling film. The temperature during the curing period was 25 ± 2 °C and the sample storage configuration favored the pozzolanic reaction and minimized carbonation.

In the SEM test, the material was only removed from the mold on the test day, that is, after 7 days of moulding, since the preparation involved only breaking the sample. With the fragments of the samples, the vacuum metallization process was carried out (coating the samples with gold), and then the samples were taken to the scanning electron microscope model Vega 3 of the Tescan brand.

For the XRD test, the sample was removed the day before, cut and sanded until they formed a disc of about 4 mm thick. After preparation, it was kept in an airtight bag, wrapped with damp towels and

cling film until the test. The parameters and analysis of the x-ray diffraction test of the pastes followed the same methodology already described in the characterization of the materials.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Mini-Slump

Figure 3 shows the average values of the spread measurements obtained in the Mini-Slump test for lime and metakaolin pastes, without and with the additives: calcium chloride, commercial additive and cement. The objective of the test was to understand how the additives influence the flow of the pastes.

Figure 3: Mini-slump of lime and metakaolin pastes

Calcium chloride (CaCl_2) increased the scattering formed after cone removal proportionally to the increase in CaCl_2 content. The cement reduced the spread in relation to the reference paste LMK and the additive maintained the spread (LMKA). A possible justification pointed out by Yuan, Zhou, Huang, Peng & Yao (2020) is related to the variation of the zeta potential of the pastes with the incorporation of the agents. In the pastes evaluated by the authors, CaCl_2 increased the zeta potential of cement pastes and plasticizing behavior was also identified in their work.

Costa, Santos, Silvestro, Rodríguez, & Kirchheim (2018) observed a reduction in spreading when calcium nitrate was used as an accelerating additive in cementitious mortars, however an increase was identified when the use of the additive was used in pastes containing cement and fly ash.

Pastes XRD

Figure 4 shows the diffractograms over time of lime and metakaolin pastes with accelerating agents at the ages of 3 and 7 days after moulding.

P - Portlandite; *M* – Monocarboaluminate; *I* – Illite;
S – Stratlingite; *D* - $\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}(\text{OH})_7\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Figure 4: Diffractogram of lime and metakaolin pastes and additives at 3 and 7 days

In the diffractograms of lime and metakaolin pastes with 3 and 7 days, the following phases were found: portlandite, monocarboaluminate, illite and hydrated calcium aluminat ($\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}(\text{OH})_7\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$). At 7 days, the LMK, LMKCe and LMKA pastes showed small peaks of stratlingite indicating its formation. In the pastes with calcium chloride, according to the mini-slump results, its non-appearance may be the result of the delay in the development of the microstructure due to the greater fluidity of these pastes. Shi & Day (2000) point out that the introduction of CaCl_2 decreases the pH of the solution, delays the dissolution of the pozzolan and accelerates the dissolution of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$.

Stratlingite is also a compound commonly found in lime-metakaolin mixture, however the age at which peaks begin to appear in the diffractogram varies. Frías & Cabrera (2001) only begin to identify peaks of this compound after 9 days, on the other hand, Zhang et al. (2020) already observed from 3 days and Bakolas et al. (2006) from 7 days. Bakolas et al. (2006) still states based on the responses of thermal analysis that the low crystallinity of the stratlingite did not allow the visualization of the peak at ages prior to 7 days.

In addition to the compounds mentioned, some authors also identify phases such as hydrogrossularite – C_3AH_6 (Zhang et al., 2020), hydrogarnet C_4AH_{13} (Gameiro et al., 2012) and CSH (Bakolas et al., 2006) over the analyzed ages. Hydrogrossularite was identified in the air cure condition (RH = 60%) used by Zhang et al. (2020). Hydrogarnet is usually formed when the curing temperature occurs at 55°C (Gameiro et al., 2012). Finally, CSH is difficult to identify in XRD due to its high degree of amorphity (Bakolas et al., 2006; Moropoulou, Cakmak, Labropoulos, Van Grieken, & Torfs, 2004; Serry, Taha, El-Hemaly, & EL-Didamony, 1984).

Comparing the ages analyzed, it is observed that few changes are seen. Portlandite peaks tend to decrease, while monocarboaluminate peaks also decrease. The same behavior is also seen in the works analyzed with advancing age, together with the emergence of stratlingite peaks, so that under wet curing conditions, the main product identified after 28 days is stratlingite ((Azeredo et al., 2015; Bakolas et al., 2006; Moisés Frías & Cabrera, 2001; Gameiro et al., 2012; Serry et al., 1984).

According to Azeredo et al. (2015), when the metakaolin content is high, more aluminum is available to form other phases such as $\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}(\text{OH})_7\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and less calcium is available to form calcium carbonate phases; and the high lime content contributes to the formation of monocarboaluminate and allows it to remain over time.

In view of the results of the diffractograms, it can be said that the gain in strength would be associated with the formation of monocarboaluminate, however, it should be highlighted the formation of amorphous phases such as CSH and stratlingite that cannot be visualized in the XRD at early ages should be highlighted ((Bakolas et al., 2006; Moropoulou et al., 2004; Serry et al., 1984), but that can contribute to the setting and hardening of the material.

Pastes SEM

Figure 5 shows the images obtained in SEM of lime and metakaolin pastes and accelerating agents at the age of 7 days in wet curing.

Figure 5: SEM images of lime and metakaolin pastes

In the images of the samples, the phases that can be identified are stratlingite (S), in the form of fine shales (M. Frías et al., 2012; Kwan, Larosa, & Grutzeck, 1995) and monocarboaluminate (M), seen as thin hexagonal plates (BANFILL, 1991). It is possible to see that the morphology of the phases present in the studied pastes has a well-defined shape. However, it is difficult to differentiate stratlingite from monocarboaluminate only through images, due to the proximity between shales and plates (Azeredo et al., 2015). Another compound that may be present in the images, but due to its hexagonal laminar shape (Nunes, Mácová, Frankeová, Ševčík, & Viani, 2018; Ruiz-Agudo & Rodríguez-Navarro, 2010; Zhang et al., 2020) was not differentiated from the other compounds, is portlandite.

Based on XRD results it can be assumed that most of the identified forms are monocarboaluminate and portlandite. Pera & Amrouz (1998) point out the formation of monocarboaluminate by the reaction between metakaolinite and CaCO_3 in mixtures of lime and calcined sludge resulting from the paper industry. Rojas & Sánchez de Rojas (2003) indicate that the formation of hydrated carbonates occurs due to the presence of CO_2 and or CaCO_3 in the pastes, which may be a consequence of the presence of CO_2 in the elaboration and mixing stages, of the relatively carbonated hydrated lime and of dissolved carbon dioxide in the mixing water.

Comparing the different materials added to lime and metakaolin pastes, it is observed that the pastes that had the longest setting time, being those with calcium chloride, have a less dense structure, so that the edges of the plates and shales appear more noticeable in figures 5-c and 5-d.

Shi & Day (2000) bring the micrograph of lime paste, volcanic ash and calcium chloride, at 28 days and cured at 35°C . In it, it is possible to observe CSH as a formless material involving hexagonal plates, which the authors associate with compounds such as hydrogarnet and $\text{C}_3\text{A}\cdot\text{CaCl}_2\cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study aimed to investigate the effect of setting accelerating agents in lime-metakaolin pastes, regarding the hardening kinetics, rheology and microstructure. For this, the microstructure of pastes was evaluated. Among the accelerating additive agents, Portland cement, calcium chloride and a commercial setting accelerator additive were used.

In the diffractograms of lime and metakaolin pastes, portlandite, monocarboaluminate, illite, hydrated calcium aluminate were observed. At 7 days, small peaks of stratlingite appeared in pastes with smaller spread in mini-slump tests. Thus, the main compound resulting from the pozzolanic reaction was monocarboaluminate, whose peaks decrease with advancing age. The formation of the stratlingite peak seems to be associated with the development of a more advanced microstructure. CSH peaks were not observed.

Finally, the microscopy images of pastes at 7 days showed thin plates and shales, whose morphology is consistent with monocarboaluminate, stratlingite and portlandite, however based on the diffractograms, it is believed that monocarboaluminate is predominant. It was also observed that less dense structures were seen in the pastes with lower water demand, which must be associated with the delay in the formation of hydrated products.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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